

From Diversity to Validity: The Statistical Fidelity of LLM-Generated Synthetic Populations

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Abstract

The extent to which large language models (LLMs) generate diverse rather than default outputs has become a key concern in research on AI alignment. However, surface level diversity does not necessarily indicate accurate representation of underlying statistical realities. In this paper, we task LLMs to create artificial personas representing migrants, and explore whether these personas reflect real-world demographic patterns rather than exhibiting only superficial diversity. Specifically, we analyze four dimensions, including migration type (internal or international), gender composition, migration origins and destinations, and migration drivers. Our results reveal that diversity does not necessarily translate into statistical alignment. While in certain cases LLMs produce seemingly balanced outputs, they may distort known distributions (e.g., over-claiming the balance between internal and international migration). On the other hand, various migration drivers are indeed represented; however, climate-related factors, which have been increasingly emphasized in recent research, are largely under-represented across models and generation settings. Results suggest that LLMs generate geographic representations through a combination of empirical patterns and semantic associations, while semantic plausibility may at times override empirical distributions, leading to biased outputs. We argue that evaluation of geo-alignment should focus not only on diversity, but on how accurately LLM outputs capture the statistical properties of geographic phenomena as well.

Keywords

large language models, geographic representation, geo-alignment, AI persona, human migration

1. Introduction

Geo-alignment of large language models (LLMs) has become an increasingly important topic in recent GIScience research, since generative AI systems are now widely used to represent space and place [1]. One common assumption is that better geo-alignment requires more diverse rather than default outputs; however, when prompted iteratively for representing geography, models sometimes repeatedly generate the same entity from a given category [2, 3, 4], suggesting limited output diversity. Greater output diversity is therefore often interpreted as evidence of geographic alignment. Nevertheless, this does not necessarily indicate that generated representations correspond to real-world geographic structures. Put differently, responses can appear well-balanced or diverse while still misrepresenting the underlying statistical properties, since in geographic context, many phenomena, such as human migration, are inherently uneven [5]. In such cases, merely producing diverse or equally represented entities is insufficient, while approximating the real-world empirical patterns shall be important. Both over-representation and under-representation lead to biased and potentially misleading conclusions.

Generative AI has increasingly been explored for creating artificial personas representing segments of the real-world population [2]. The empirical patterns or distributional shifts observed from these personas, on the other hand, can reflect the extent to which they are statistically realistic and empirically grounded for downstream applications. In this paper, we move beyond “diversity” and examine whether LLM representations of geographic phenomena, particularly human migration, correspond to real-world

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demographic statistics. Human migration provides a suitable case study in our paper, since migration flow is inherently uneven, making it easier to examine whether LLM-generated representations capture real-world statistical structures or simply produce superficially diverse outputs. Specifically, we collect LLM-generated artificial personas representing migrants, and analyze key statistical characteristics. We design a series of controlled generations using different models, with different output modes including batch generation (multiple personas in a single response) and sequential generation (one persona at a time). We then compare the statistics of generated personas with real-world demographic patterns. In Section 2 we will elaborate on our methodology.

2. Data and Methods

2.1. Data

In this paper, we use the latest *World Migration Report* published by the International Organization for Migration (IOM) as an empirical reference for comparison. The report provides global statistics and evidence-based analyses on human migration processes [5]. To investigate the extent to which LLM generations align with it, we focus on four key dimensions that capture different aspects of migration as a geographic phenomenon: migration type (internal or international), gender composition of migrants, migration origin and destination distributions, as well as key migration drivers. These dimensions are selected because they are both central to migration studies and consistently documented in the IOM report. Table 1 summarizes the empirical migration patterns used as references in our analysis.

Table 1

Key human migration patterns reported by IOM.

Aspect	Empirical finding
Migration type	Internal migration accounts for the vast majority of global human migration
Gender composition	Women account for approximately 48% of international migrants
Origin & destination	Migration flows are concentrated in several major corridors, with countries such as India, Mexico, Russia, China, and Bangladesh among the major origins and the United States, Germany, Saudi Arabia, Russia, the UK among the major destinations
Migration drivers	Labor remains the dominant driver of international migration, while environmental or climate migration has also become a main concern

Based on these dimensions, we generate artificial migrant personas using LLMs. The generated personas are subsequently analyzed and compared to the reported patterns.

2.2. Experimental Design

In our approach, we query two models within the GPT-5 family, namely GPT-5.2 and GPT-5.4, to generate artificial personas representing migrants. We include these two models to reduce the possibility that our findings are driven by specific features of one single model. For each experimental setting, we collect 200 personas from each model. The generated personas are designed to analyze key migration-related attributes, including origin and destination, migration drivers, and gender.

Different dimensions of our experiment require slightly different output scopes. To explore whether LLMs can reproduce the dominance of internal migration, we explicitly instruct LLMs to consider both forms of migration. For the remaining three dimensions including gender composition, origin and destination distribution, and migration drivers, we prompt LLMs to focus only on international migration to match the scope of the corresponding statistics provided by IOM.

Since LLM outputs are naturally sensitive to conversational structure and contextual information [6, 7], we consider two generation modes. In the sequential generation setting, a model generates one persona in each response, and the process is repeated 200 times. In the batch generation setting, a model generates all 200 personas within a single response. Rather than assuming one mode to be inherently superior, we include both settings to reduce the possibility that a single generation

Listing 1: User prompt for persona generation: an example.

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Generate a list of 200 realistic personas that represent international migrants. Note that internal migration is excluded. For each persona, consider five features with specific data types:
1. Origin of migration: geographic coordinates;
2. Destination of migration: geographic coordinates;
3. Factors driving migration: list;
4. Gender: binary;
5. Occupation: text.
Output a nested Python dictionary containing all personas and those 5 attributes without giving any explanation or additional text.
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mode systematically shapes the resulting population compositions. All experiments are conducted using the default temperature settings of the corresponding models in order to preserve their standard conversational behavior.

Listing 1 presents the user prompt used for international migrant persona generation under the batch-generation setting as an illustration. The prompt specifies the attributes associated with each migrant persona and the required output format.

With the LLM-generated personas, we explore their migration patterns and compare them with the statistical results from IOM. For migration type, gender composition, and origin and destination distributions, we directly conduct statistical aggregation on these personas. Migration type is classified into internal or international based on whether the origin and destination locations fall within the same country. Based on this, the origin and destination pairs are computed from the frequency of corresponding countries. Gender distributions are obtained through simple aggregation.

Migration drivers require a different analytical approach because they are represented as open-text rather than predefined categories. To capture their semantic patterns, we compute text embeddings for extracted migration drivers using *text-embedding-3-large* model. Here, “embeddings” are vector representations that encode semantic information and facilitate similarity comparisons between textual expressions [8]. We subsequently project these embeddings into a two-dimensional space with t-SNE [9] for visualization, and also interpret the dominant clusters after conducting *k*-means clustering ($k = 10$) on the embeddings [10]. This allows us to identify dominant thematic patterns in the generated migration drivers and compare with the IOM report.

3. Results

Figure 1a presents the proportions of internal migrants in the artificial personas generated by different models under different output modes. When personas are generated sequentially, both models produce migrant populations dominated by internal migration, broadly aligning with statistical migration patterns documented in the IOM report. In contrast, batch generation produces substantially more balanced distributions between internal and international migration. Although these outputs appear more diverse at the surface level, they deviate from the observed dominance of internal migration. This result also indicates that, being influenced by output context, LLM-generated geographic representations can vary substantially across generation modes. However, we emphasize that this should not be interpreted as evidence that one output mode is universally preferable, since different tendencies emerge for other demographic and spatial dimensions. As Figure 1b shows, batch generation broadly approximates the near-balanced gender distribution reported in migration statistics, whereas sequential generation by GPT-5.2 produces excessively higher proportion of female migrants by 28 percentage points. Furthermore, origin and destination distributions generated under all settings are dispersed and less consistent with major empirical migration corridors. Certain origins such as Ethiopia and Nigeria, as well as destinations such as China and Spain, are over-represented despite their comparatively

Figure 1: Basic statistics of LLM-generated personas: (a) proportion of internal migration; (b) gender distribution of international migrants.

weaker role in global migration statistics. Taken together, these results suggest that LLM representation is not governed by a single stable logic. Instead, apart from statistical patterns, different factors like semantic structure can also shape the representations. Under some settings, LLMs do produce diverse and balanced outputs, but such outputs may distort known distributions. Geographic phenomena, such as human migration, can be inherently uneven, while balanced or highly diverse outputs may themselves become statistically misleading. We highlight that geographic alignment in LLM-generated personas cannot be fully inferred from diversity alone, but statistical fidelity also plays a crucial role.

Figure 2 visualizes the embedding projections of migration drivers extracted from generated personas together with the corresponding clustering centers. Across all experimental settings, labor-related factors dominate the generated migration narratives. In detail, employment opportunities, income, education, remittances, and family-related motivations consistently form the largest semantic clusters. In contrast, climate- or environment-related migration factors are largely absent. Although environmental migration has received increasing attention in migration research and policy discussions [11], explicit references to climate change, environmental degradation, drought, flooding, or related factors appear only rarely across generated personas. This finding suggests that LLM representations of migration are shaped not only by empirical demographic patterns, but also by dominant semantic information embedded in training corpora. As a result, migration narratives that have only recently become prominent in contemporary geographic discussions may still remain under-represented in generated personas, as they were not widely mentioned in past discourses.

4. Discussion and Conclusion

This paper investigates whether LLM-generated migrant personas align with demographic statistics. Using personas generated by GPT-5.2 and GPT-5.4 under batch or sequential generation modes, we compare the resulting representations with empirical migration patterns documented in the IOM report across four dimensions: migration type, gender composition, origin and destination distributions, as well as migration drivers. Rather than treating diversity as a sufficient indicator of geo-alignment, we move beyond and examine whether generated personas reproduce the statistical characteristics of the underlying phenomenon. Results suggest that these representations generated by LLMs emerge from the interaction between empirical regularities and semantic information embedded in training corpora and broader discourse. Across several dimensions, outputs that appear balanced or diverse do not necessarily correspond to observed migration statistics. On the contrary, they may still be biased and misleading by distorting the empirical migration patterns. This observation highlights an important distinction between diversity and statistical fidelity. For inherently uneven geographic phenomena such as human migration, increasing representational diversity does not automatically improve geographic alignment and may, in some cases, reduce it. When LLM-generated personas are employed for simulation, scenario exploration, or decision support, such generations may still commit the marginalization of minorities or the over-hype of certain phenomena. We highlight that evaluations

Figure 2: Embedding projections of migration drivers and 10 clustering centers with representative phrases under each experimental setting: (a) gpt-5.2 model, batch generation; (b) gpt-5.2 model, sequential generation; (c) gpt-5.4 model, batch generation; (d) gpt-5.4 model, sequential generation.

of geo-alignment should consider not only the variety of generated outputs, but also the extent to which AI systems reproduce empirically observed distributions and spatial structures.

Despite these contributions, several limitations remain. First, this study focuses exclusively on migration. While it does provide a useful test case because of its well-documented and highly uneven statistical pattern, the extent to which our findings generalize to other geographic domains remains unclear. Future work could apply the framework to additional phenomena. Second, only 200 personas are generated under each experimental setting. Given that the number of countries and territories worldwide exceeds the sample size, country-level origin and destination frequencies may be sensitive to sampling variation. Larger generated populations may provide more stable estimates of spatial distributions and demographic composition. Third, the present study evaluates LLM outputs under unconstrained generation settings, allowing models to generate migrant personas solely from their internal representations. An interesting direction for future work would be to investigate whether statistical alignment improves when empirical migration statistics are explicitly provided to the model as contextual information. Such experiments could help distinguish limitations of model knowledge from those arising from generation strategies, prompting conditions, or hallucinations, etc. Finally, although we address origin and destination distributions, we do not explicitly analyze migration origin-destination pairs across the globe. Future research could compare generated migration corridors with observed migration networks, thereby extending the notion of geographic alignment from distributions to geographic relationships.

Overall, this paper argues that evaluating geographic alignment requires moving beyond diversity alone. Understanding how LLMs statistically and semantically reconstruct geographic phenomena is equally important, particularly when those phenomena are inherently uneven and shaped by evolving social narratives.

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Declaration on Generative AI

During the preparation of this work, the authors used GPT-5.2 and GPT-5.4 to collect the migrant personas through API. The authors also used ChatGPT for some grammar and spelling check. After using these tools, the authors reviewed and edited the content as needed and take full responsibility for the publication's content.

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